

UNIVERSITY OF UYO TEACHING HOSPITAL

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Our Ref: UUTH/AD/S/96/VOL.XXI/253

Date: December 20, 2018

Your Ref:

UNIVERSITY OF UYO TEACHING HOSPITAL, UYO INSTITUTIONAL HEALTH RESEARCH ETHICAL COMMITTEE (IHREC)

APPROVAL CERTIFICATE LETTER

Principal Investigator: **DR. CHRISTIE AKWAOWO**

Protocol Title: "IMPROVING TB CASE FINDING USING COMMUNITY INVOLVEMENT TO INCREASE UPTAKE OF SERVICES IN AKWA IBOM STATE"

STATUS

The University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, Uyo Institutional Review Committee has reviewed your protocol title: "IMPROVING TB CASE FINDING USING COMMUNITY INVOLVEMENT TO INCREASE UPTAKE OF SERVICES IN AKWA IBOM STATE"

The research protocol described above has been approved by the University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, Uyo Institutional Health Research Ethical Committee (IHREC) as indicated.

Onwuezobe, Eseoghene Irene Esq.
Secretary, IHREC
UUTH, Uyo